

ISic3052

I.Sicily inscription 3052

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo / Pulera)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea",
inventory 15395

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ΦΙΛΙΚΚΩΣ

Apparatus

Meligunìs Lipára XII

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645406

PHI 334172

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0807

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 70
Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1991. Meligunìs Lipára V. Scavi nella necropoli
greca di Lipari. Rome. At 150 cippo 2161 fig.330b

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